

INVOLVEMENT OF DUAL EDUCATION IN IMPROVING EDUCATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS

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Abstract. In this article, the state of training of advanced specialists in the use of innovative educational technologies, the development of the Dual education system and the theoretical aspects of foreign experiences, the mechanism of organizing and implementing Dual education training, dual education in creating innovative educational content are presented. Possibilities of engaging in training, scientific and methodological recommendations are given.

Key words. Dual education, foreign experience, innovation, specialist, educational technologies, professional education.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассмотрено состояние подготовки передовых специалистов по использованию инновационных образовательных технологий, развитие системы дуального образования и теоретические аспекты зарубежного опыта, механизм организации и реализации обучения дуальному образованию, дуальное образование в создании инновационного образовательного процесса. содержание представлено. Даны возможности проведения обучения, даны научные и методические рекомендации.

Ключевые слова. Дуальное образование, зарубежный опыт, инновации, специалист, образовательные технологии, профессиональное образование.

Achieving state independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan has chosen a specific path of social, economic, political recovery and development, the need to improve the system of continuing education, the creation of a national system of training highly qualified personnel meeting high professional, spiritual and moral requirements. The

tasks and directions for achieving this goal are described in detail in the National Training Program, and the role and importance of production in training, which is one of the main components of the national model, deserves special attention today. Production is the main customer, which determines the need for personnel, as well as the requirements for the quality and level of their training, a participant in the process of financial and logistical support of the training system. The development of the integration of the production and education systems has been identified as one of the priorities in the development of the training system. This topical issue requires the establishment of mutually beneficial cooperation between industrial enterprises and educational institutions.

It is known that the system of technical educational institutions, which is one of the main links in the system of continuing education, is responsible for the training of highly qualified specialists required for the economy of our country. It is no secret that the establishment of strong ties between manufacturing enterprises and educational institutions, in other words, the establishment of mutually beneficial social cooperation is one of the urgent issues of today in order to fulfill this responsible task. The following data, based on our initial observations and scientific analysis, once again confirm the urgency of this problem:

- low level of participation of employers in the creation of qualification requirements for technical education institutions, developed for the training of qualified specialists in educational institutions;
- The existence of imbalances between the skills and abilities of graduates of educational institutions and the requirements of industrial enterprises;
- There are difficulties in organizing and conducting production operations at enterprises and institutions;
- Inadequacy of training programs designed to train qualified specialists to the requirements of the changing labor market;

- The existence of imbalances between equipment and technology in production and the material and technical base of educational institutions;
- Lack of development of methods for studying and analyzing the requirements of the labor market and the requirements for knowledge, skills and abilities of specialists, etc.
- Insufficient involvement of highly qualified specialists from manufacturing enterprises in the process of training qualified specialists;
- Professional development or retraining courses for masters and teachers of special subjects are not organized on the basis of manufacturing enterprises;

In our opinion, the shortcomings and problems listed above can be addressed through the establishment of mutually beneficial cooperation with production in the system of technical education institutions. To do this, we believe that it is necessary to create a scientific and methodological basis for the organization of social cooperation in educational institutions, and we want to focus our research on solving this problem. In creating educational content, it is important to first analyze the labor market in the area where the educational institution is located. To do this, every educational institution must master the methodology of labor market analysis and have experts in this field. Economic and social changes in Uzbekistan have led to the formation of the labor market and educational services, which in turn has changed the strategy of vocational training.

To take into account the constantly changing requirements of educational institutions, the labor market and employers for a skilled workforce, the skills and knowledge of trained professionals for the effective functioning of the system of educational institutions, review curricula in accordance with these changes, improve qualification requirements, curricula and programs.

To do this, the system of technical education institutions and educational institutions need to systematically study the labor market at the national level, primarily at the local, ie district level.

The main features and indicators of the labor market.

The concept of the labor market also includes the job market because the demand for them and the supply in the labor market are constant.

For analysis, the labor market can be divided into external and internal types. The external labor market is characterized by inter-enterprise movement of labor. In this case, the workers, for various reasons, usually move from one enterprise to another and retain their occupations.

The domestic market usually operates within a single enterprise (firm) with vacancies. This is often interrelated with layoffs of workers, expansion of production, increase in the exchange rate. Some of the vacancies will be claimed by enterprise employees and employers will offer vacancies to their employees. Within this market, the workforce can move in both vertical and horizontal directions.

In a vertical shift, workers can be raised or lowered in their position. In the horizontal shift (shift), workers acquire knowledge of additional occupations and production processes. . Demand and supply of labor is one of the main categories (elements) of the labor market..

Demand -reflects the need for employees by enterprises to fill vacancies. First of all, it depends on changes in production volume, labor productivity, labor costs, and is formed by categories (occupations) of employees. Labor supply is determined by the number of job seekers, depending on the number and composition of the economically active population.

The concept of economically active population (labor force) represents the part of the population that provides the labor force needed to produce goods and services. The number of economically active population is determined for a given period and includes the employed and the unemployed.

The purpose of the labor market analysis- is to study the needs of social partners in qualified professionals, training by employers in the areas of occupation and vocational training, the level of knowledge and skills, trends in the current and

future needs of professionals and their proposals. The results of the analysis can serve as a basis for improving the standards of educational institutions, training plans and programs, as well as the development of strategies for the development of technical educational institutions at the level of the system of technical higher education.

The main tasks of labor market analysis.

The labor market analysis curriculum should be developed by educational institutions and should include the following:

- a description of the direction of the supply and demand for the workforce in general and in terms of professions, focusing on the professions of specialists trained in educational institutions;- Assess the quality of the trained specialists in terms of professions and specialties, their level of training, knowledge, skills and abilities to meet the requirements of employers;

- identification of sustainable development directions of the regional economy in order to identify future plans for the training of specialists and the development of services for enterprises and the informal sector of the economy; - to anticipate and prevent socio-economic conflicts between supply and demand for labor. At the same time, it is necessary to identify the most pressing problems in the provision of enterprises and the district with qualified specialists, and to identify possible solutions at the level of social cooperation in the system of educational institutions.

The object of labor market analysis

Objects of labor market analysis:

- External and internal labor markets of the district (city), because the problems of employment and labor demand are not limited to the scope of the enterprise, but also the current economic situation in the district (city) and the socio-economic development of the district (city). directions;- At the district (city) level, the analysis of the labor market and the needs of specialists for knowledge, skills and abilities is carried out with the participation of social partners of educational institutions.

Analysis of the need for professional knowledge, skills and abilities. An important part of the labor market analysis is to identify the needs of employers for the knowledge, skills and competencies acquired by graduates. The main purpose of the analysis of these needs is: a) determination of the demand for personnel received by educational institutions;

b) identification of priority areas and professions for training;

c) identification of areas for the development of requirements for professionals, knowledge, skills and abilities. All of this information will be used to improve the standards of educational institutions, training programs and curricula. Questionnaires for the analysis of the labor market are attached to the monograph.

LIST OF REFERENCES USED

1. Khodjaboev A.R. Scientific and pedagogical foundations of the educational and methodological complex for the preparation of a labor teacher: Abstract of the thesis. dis. ... Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences. T.: 1992. - 42 b. Chistyakova S.N. Pedagogical support of professional self-determination of schoolchildren - S. N. Chistyakova, P. S. Lerner, N. F. Rodichev, E. V. Titova. Moscow: New school, 2004.

2. Chistyakova S.N. On the principles of profile education and the problems of their implementation - Profile education in the context of the modernization of school education. Sat. scientific Proceedings of S. N. Chistyakov. M.: IOSO RAO, 2003.

3. Klimov E. A. The path to professionalism E. A. Klimov. Moscow: Flinta, 2003.

4. Sharifovna, T. Z., Khamidovna, S. K., Bakhtiyorovna, T. B., & Fakhritdinovna, M. S. (2020). Improving Higher Education Through Integrated Learning, Features Of An Integrated Lesson. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*, 7(03), 3052-3064.

5. Sharifovna, T. Z., & Bakhriniso, T. (2020). Modernization of higher education by solving integration problems. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*, 8(12 Part II), 44-49.

6. Comenius Ya.A. Selected pedagogical works: In 2 vols.-M.: Pedagogy, 1982.
-T.: 2. - 576 p. Kotovskaya M.G. Social partnership and gender in the Soviet era.
7. Kryukova E.A. Personally - developing educational technologies: nature, design, implementation. Monograph. - Volgograd. Change, 2000. - 97 p.